

Analysis of Bromide by a Kinetic Method

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Manuscript received 23 May 1989, revised 26 March 1990, accepted 22 August 1990

Bromide catalysed oxidation of As^{III} and Sb^{III} by Ce^{IV} in acid solution has been utilised to develop a kinetic method for the analysis of bromide in the range of 1–100 mg dm⁻³ by spectrophotometric technique. Interferences of various ions were also studied.

THERE are several methods of analysis of bromide estimated to the millimolar level¹. Methods of analysis of bromide below this concentration level are important in view of the presence of bromide in millimolar quantities in sea water, its use in medicine, and in the manufacture of tetraethyllead, photographic films and papers.

Iodide catalysis of cerium(IV)-arsenic(III) reaction is well-known². Indeed, the catalytic method has become a standard practice for the determination of iodide at very low concentrations in a large variety of samples. However, there are virtually no studies on bromide catalysis of the cerium(IV)-arsenic(III) reaction although bromide in very small quantity is known to catalyse the reaction. Such bromide catalysis may be the basis of a kinetic catalytic procedure for the estimation of bromide in the μg range. In the present study, bromide catalysis of oxidation of arsenic(III) or antimony(III) by cerium(IV) has been examined in detail. It is found that the bromide catalysis parallels that of iodide and can form the basis of a kinetic method for the bromide determination. The bromide catalysis is greater in case of antimony(III) than that in arsenic(III).

Experimental

Reagent grade chemicals were used and double-distilled water was used throughout. The Ce^{IV} stock solution was made by dissolution of cerium(IV) ammonium sulphate (AnalaR) in dilute sulphuric acid and was standardised with iron(II) ammonium sulphate (AnalaR) solution. The As^{III} stock solution was obtained by dissolving As^{III} oxide (AnalaR) in dilute sodium hydroxide solution which was neutralised with acid and standardised with potassium iodate solution. The Sb^{III} stock solution was prepared by dissolving antimony(III) oxide in perchloric acid and was standardised with potassium bromate solution. The stock solutions were diluted as required before use. The catalyst stock solution was obtained by dissolving potassium bromide (AnalaR) in water. Ionic strength was kept constant with sodium perchlorate.

The kinetics of bromide catalysed Ce^{IV} oxidation of As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) in aqueous perchloric acid solution at an ionic strength of 1.1 mol dm⁻³ were followed spectrophotometrically by periodically measuring the Ce^{IV} absorption at 360 nm. The reaction conditions as mentioned in Table 1 were used for kinetics. The application of Beer's law in respect of the Ce^{IV} absorption under the reaction conditions at 25° had earlier been found to obey Beer's law in the range of 0.50×10^{-4} to 6.0×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³ of Ce^{IV} ($\epsilon = 3150 \pm 1.5\% \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$). A Hitachi 150-20 spectrophotometer was used to follow the kinetics by placing the cell containing the reaction solution in the thermostated cell compartment. Kinetic runs involved variation of one variable at a time keeping the others constant. For analytical purposes, runs were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions with the concentration of the reductant in excess over the Ce^{IV} concentration. All measurements were made at constant acidity using a constant concentration of perchloric acid in addition to the constant minimum amount of sulphuric acid used in the preparation of the Ce^{IV} stock solution. The pseudo-first order rate constants at constant acidity and constant ionic strength were found from the slopes of plots of $\log(a-x)$ vs time which were linear well beyond 80% of reaction. Rate constants were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Results and Discussion

The iodide catalysed Ce^{IV}-As^{III} reaction has been the subject of several studies² and very small quantities down to ng level can be measured in this way. The bromide catalysis of the Ce^{IV} oxidation of As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) in aqueous perchloric acid parallels the results of similar iodide catalysed Ce^{IV}-As^{III} reactions. In the iodide catalysed case, it was found that the order of either reactants depended on the relative concentration with respect to the other reactants. When the concentration one of the reactants was smaller by a factor of five or larger, its order was unity and when the concentration was around five-fold excess, the order approached zero. The order in catalyst (iodide) when it was present in extremely small concentrations ($\sim 10^{-8}$ or lower),

was unity; the order decreasing to a fraction as its relative concentration with respect to arsenic(III) increased. Increasing acid concentration increased the rate, while the products Ce^{III} and As^V had little effect. These results are paralleled in the present case of bromide catalysis of the Ce^{IV}-As^{III} (or Ce^{IV}-Sb^{III}) reaction. The orders were found at 25° at constant Br⁻, acid and ionic strength conditions of [Br⁻]=5.0 × 10⁻⁵, [HClO₄]=0.50 and I=2.0 mol dm⁻³ respectively, except when the effect of any of these variables was under study. Two extreme conditions were employed: (i) [As^{III}] or [Sb^{III}] >> [Ce^{IV}] and (ii) [Ce^{IV}] >> [As^{III}] or [Sb^{III}]. At constant substrate (As^{III} or Sb^{III}) concentration of 2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³, the [Ce^{IV}] order between 0.50 × 10⁻³ and 4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ was ~1; its order was zero between 1.0 × 10⁻³ and 7.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ at constant substrate concentration of 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³. The substrate order was unity at constant [Ce^{IV}]=4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³ in the range of 2.0 × 10⁻⁴ to 6.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³; the substrate order was zero in the range of 0.50 × 10⁻² to 4.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³ at constant [Ce^{IV}]=1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³. The order in [H⁺] when the substrate concentration (2.0 × 10⁻² mol dm⁻³) being in excess over Ce^{IV} (1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³), was fractional (~0.9) in the range 0.25–1.25 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid; the order in [H⁺] was again fractional (~0.7) in the same range of 0.25–1.25 mol dm⁻³ perchloric acid under conditions of excess oxidant ([Ce^{IV}]=1.0 × 10⁻³ and [As^{III}] or [Sb^{III}]=4.0 × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³). The order in bromide concentration, under both the conditions, was fractional (~0.4 when the substrate was in excess and ~0.5 when the oxidant was excess). Under both the conditions, initially added products did not have any significant effect on the reaction. The effects of increasing ionic strength and temperature were examined under conditions of excess reductant ([As^{III}]=2.0 × 10⁻²; [Br⁻]=5.0 × 10⁻⁵ and [Ce^{IV}]=1.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³). Ionic strength between 2.0 and 4.0 mol dm⁻³ increased the pseudo-first order rate constant from 1.87 to 2.30 s⁻¹. The pseudo-first order rate constants of 1.87, 3.46, 4.35, 6.14 and 7.68 s⁻¹ at 25, 30, 35, 40 and 45° led to the activation energy of 62.6 (±0.5) kJ mol⁻¹.

Thus it may be seen that the results of the Br⁻ catalysis of the Ce^{IV}-As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) reaction are similar to the corresponding iodide catalysis and, therefore, a similar mechanism² may be seen to apply (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

Under the condition of excess substrate concentration, the scheme consisting of steps (1) to (3) alone may be seen to apply, as oxidation of Br⁻ beyond Br⁰ (to Br⁺) is relatively less likely. This would also explain the fractional dependence on Br⁻ concentration under such conditions. The fractional dependence on Br⁻ may also be due in part, to the formation of complexes of Br⁻ with substrate which can take place to a much less extent in the case of iodide catalysis. Moreover, the order in substrate, under conditions of excess substrate concentration, is also zero.

It is also apparent that, as As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) and Ce^{IV} are in competition for some intermediate oxidation state of bromide, for the catalytic reaction to accurately reflect the analytical concentration of iodide, As^{III} must be present in excess over Ce^{IV}. True to such requirements, under conditions of excess substrate concentration, the pseudo-first order constants (k₁) of the reaction, Ce^{IV} oxidation of As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) catalysed by bromide, is a linear function of the bromide concentration under conditions of constant acidity and ionic strength (Table 1), and a kinetic catalytic method for Br⁻ is feasible.

TABLE 1—BROMIDE-CATALYSED Ce^{IV}-As^{III}/Sb^{III} REACTION AT 25°

Ce ^{IV} -As ^{III}		Ce ^{IV} -Sb ^{III}	
[Br ⁻] × 10 ⁵ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹	[Br ⁻] × 10 ⁴ M	k ₁ × 10 ³ s ⁻¹
0.0	2.81	0.0	4.22
0.5	3.26	0.5	9.12
1.0	3.97	1.0	10.9
2.0	4.21	2.0	12.9
5.0	5.12	4.0	16.8
7.5	5.93	6.0	22.1
10.0	6.91	8.0	25.9
15.0	7.93	10.0	29.8
20.0	9.50	12.0	35.5
25.0	10.80	15.0	42.2
		18.0	46.1
		20.0	48.9

[Ce^{IV}]=1 × 10⁻⁴ M, [As^{III}]=2.0 × 10⁻² M, [HClO₄]=0.50 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 × 10⁻² M, I=1.1 M

[Ce^{IV}]=1.0 × 10⁻⁴ M, [Sb^{III}]=1.0 × 10⁻² M, [HClO₄]=0.50 M, [H₂SO₄]=1.0 × 10⁻² M, I=1.1 M

A calibration curve of k₁ vs [Br⁻] under a known set of conditions of concentrations of oxidant, substrate, acid and temperature (as in Table 1) is made. The reaction is repeated under similar conditions in presence of the solution of bromide of unknown concentration and the resulting value of k₁ used to obtain the concentration of bromide from the calibration curve. Alternatively, under the conditions of the reaction, after a definite interval of time (say 5 min) one of the concentrations, in this case that of Ce^{IV}, measured both in the presence and absence of a known amount of the catalyst. Such data, again, lead to a calibration curve as that shown in Fig. 1 and the unknown concentration of bromide can be obtained from such a graph.

For routine measurements, the latter procedure is recommended. However, as shown in Fig. 1, for

Fig. 1. Calibration curve for analysis of Br^- by kinetic method in the case of (◻) $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-As}^{\text{III}}$ and (○) $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Sb}^{\text{III}}$ reactions.

concentrations higher than around $1.2 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Sb}^{\text{III}}$ reaction) and $2.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ ($\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-As}^{\text{III}}$ reaction), under conditions of Table 1, deviations from linearity occur and the method is not satisfactory. The deviations are caused presumably because of the lack of excess concentrations of substrate whereby the conditions of total Br^- taking part in the catalytic cycle do not obtain. Furthermore, apparently a higher oxidant concentration than has been used for calibration purposes needs to be used as this concentration almost matches the Br^- concentration. In the determination of Br^- , small variations in substrate concentration do not affect the method. However, acidity and oxidant concentration should be the same. It is noteworthy that this method enables determination of sizable quantities of Br^- ranging from 1 to $100 \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$.

Method recommended for analysis: A set comprising of known concentrations of Ce^{IV} , As^{III} (or Sb^{III}) as the case may be, HClO_4 and KBr (1.0×10^{-4} , 2.0×10^{-3} , 0.50 and $5.0 \times 10^{-5} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ respectively as in Table 1; a constant amount of $1.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sulphuric acid used in the preparation of Ce^{IV} stock solution is also present) is thermostated and mixed. The absorbance reading is taken at the 1st min with the same concentrations of reactants and acid, the concentration of bromide is varied, the reading at the 1st min being

taken in each case. Taking the difference in absorbance between the catalysed and uncatalysed reactions as Δx , a calibration curve of Δx vs $[\text{Br}^-]$ is plotted (Fig. 1). This plot is then used for determining unknown concentrations of bromide. The results of such an analysis are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RESULTS OF KINETIC METHOD OF ANALYSIS OF BROMIDE: BROMIDE-CATALYSED $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-As}^{\text{III}}/\text{Sb}^{\text{III}}$ REACTION AT 25°

$\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-As}^{\text{III}}$ $\text{Br}^- \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$			$\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Sb}^{\text{III}}$ $\text{Br}^- \mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$		
Taken	Found*	S.D.	Taken	Found*	S.D.
0.24	0.22	± 0.03	1.20	1.21	± 0.01
0.89	0.88	± 0.01	2.79	2.76	± 0.03
1.75	1.80	± 0.02	4.39	4.35	± 0.02
2.08	2.10	± 0.01	6.50	6.47	± 0.01
5.20	5.10	± 0.02	8.79	8.73	± 0.01
6.95	6.90	± 0.02	10.38	10.40	± 0.01
8.23	8.29	± 0.03	19.98	20.01	± 0.03
11.75	11.73	± 0.01	35.96	35.91	± 0.02
15.09	15.10	± 0.01	51.94	51.97	± 0.01
16.78	16.80	± 0.02	62.32	62.41	± 0.03
19.18	19.10	± 0.03	71.91	71.82	± 0.03
			87.90	87.86	± 0.02
			95.88	95.86	± 0.01

*Average of five sets.

The interference of some ions was also tested in the above method of analysis of bromide. Apart from the reductants which reduce Ce^{IV} and the oxidants which oxidise $\text{As}^{\text{III}}/\text{Sb}^{\text{III}}$, it was found that Fe^{III} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Tl^{I} , Zn^{II} , sulphate do not interfere in the Br^- catalysed $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-As}^{\text{III}}$ reaction, while cyanide, thiocyanate, acetate, iodide, chloride, Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Hg^{I} , Ag^{I} , Cr^{III} , V , Mo^{II} , Hg^{II} and Pd^{II} interfere. In the Br^- catalysed $\text{Ce}^{\text{IV}}\text{-Sb}^{\text{III}}$ reaction, cyanide, sulphate, Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mo^{II} , V have no effect, while Fe^{III} , Mn^{II} , Tl^{I} , Hg^{I} , Cr^{III} , Ag^{I} , Hg^{II} , Pd^{II} , thiocyanate, acetate, chloride and iodide interfere. In all the cases, interferences were examined upto a concentration of $4.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ of the diverse ion.

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